

“Leadership and Challenges” An Empirical Study on Economic Growth in the Field of Financial Technology in the Present Era

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Akshatha, BH, and R. Uma Maheshwari. “Leadership And Challenges’ An Empirical Study on Economic Growth in the Field of Financial Technology in the Present Era.” Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities, vol. 7, no. 2, 2019, pp. 59–61.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3669470>

B.H. Akshatha & R. Uma Maheshwari

2nd-Year, M.com, Sri Aurobindo College

Abstract

Finance plays a significant role in the world. Technology in the finance field has made tremendous changes in the economy. Without adopting innovation strategies, companies will lose their competitive advantage in an increasingly commoditized world. There is no limit to lose, as technology change accelerates exponentially, and new digital platforms and devices are emerging. Furthermore, the expectations of the new generation are such that companies must keep up with the pace of change or lose relevance. They adopt their lifestyles to each new technological invention, and in the midst of all this, we need to keep in mind the problems of digital change such as customer relationship, increased competition, and constant digital engagement with the consumer. These paper technological inventions have revolutionized each sector of society by reducing human labor, bringing efficiency, and increasing productivity. This research is a stepping stone in exploring the interaction between Fintech.

Fintech, the word which originates from “finance” and “technology”, designates currently a novel, innovative, and emerging field which attracts attention from the publicity. Through this paper, we also identify drivers of fin-tech and put them in the context of financial and digital innovation research. There by we provide an objective understanding of fin-tech, how it is reflected in popular media. As the world becomes progressively more connected through the internet of everything. The emergence of fin-tech is beginning to disrupt the financial world with transformative changes. The unique consumer behavior and banking habits of millennials, coupled with their pro-technology attitude, facilitate the rapidly advancing disruptive revolution of fin-tech. Banks and financial institutions alike have been adopting innovative technology to cater to the ubiquitous use of mobile devices. As many fin-tech companies accelerate their customers with more convenient financial services experiences at much lower costs.

Keywords: Financial technology, Competitive Advantage, Efficiency, Convenient, Digital, Revolution.

Introduction

Fintech is a combination of the terms “finance” and “technology” and refers to any business that uses technology to enhance or automate financial services and processes. This is a broad and rapidly growing industry serving both consumers and businesses. From mobile banking to crypto currency and investment apps, fin-tech has wide applications. One driving factor is that many traditional banks are

supporters and adopters of the technology, actively investing in, or acquiring with fin-tech startups because it is easier to give tech-savvy customers what they want, while also moving the industry forward and staying pertinent. Customers, especially millennial, expect money transfer, lending, loan management, and investing to be easy, secure, and scalable, preferably without the support of a person or the visit of any bank. In contrast to conventional banks, fin-tech startups work flexible and fast when it comes to implementing new services based on varying demands.

The objective of the Study

- To study the concept of financial services and usage
- To know the benefits and usage of financial services packages for the companies
- To understand the challenges in the implementation of financial services
- To provide useful suggestions for adopting financial services

Research Methodology

Secondary data – a publication from various websites, journals, research papers, surveys which focused on different aspects of fin-tech.

Impact of Technology in Financial Services

Technology has changed the complete perspective of the financial sector’s operations. People now will never even remember the old traditional ways, where the working or carrying the finance operations was a tedious task. Every operation now days are happening in the finger tips itself. And this trend is likely to increase in the coming days. Especially in the bank - from developing intelligent digital assistants, providing seamless services and building data models, acting on lending decisions, and enhancing customer relationship, security with advanced recognition techniques.

The rise of fin-tech has changed every characteristic of financial services and banking.

- **Loans:** With the start of fin-tech companies, loans, and allied services can be easily availed by consumers.
- **Payment Services:** Now, payments are made online using the internet or through smart phones, alleviating the need for commercial accounts. Money can be transferred straight to the bank account, which reduces the chances of fraud and transaction fees.
- **Wealth Administration:** Fintech software helps in comparing options to create the best investment plans for personal finance.
- **Remittance Transfers:** Over the years, fin-tech companies have strived to make these inbound and outbound businesses simple and inexpensive.
- **Insurance Services:** Acquiring insurance has now become a less complex process.

The Fintech Revolution in India

Like every other country, India has also experienced the strong impact of financial technology in the banking and finance sector. For India, which is a cash-driven

Country, this is an initiative towards creating a cashless society. With a range of fin-tech services software, it has changed the way the people carry out daily transactions and handle their currency. This vigorous transformation brought upon by the involvement of technology and the financial sector has opened a gateway for the fin-tech ecosystem in India. In below ten years, it has become one of the most active sectors in India with the investments and funding from big companies like Facebook, Google, and Whatsapp. In addition, native firms playing a significant role in the development of this massive industry include Paytm, Phonepe, Mobikwik, and Free charge, etc. According to a report by the National Association of Software and Services Companies (NASSCOM), there are about 400 companies in India with excess amount of foreign investments invested in fin-tech market. As per the report, the Fintech software and services market of India is anticipated to grow into an \$8 Billion market by 2020. It is likely to grow by 1.7 times.

Financial Technology Trends

- Block chain/crypto – companies are leveraging block chain technology for financial services.
- Digitized bank – payment processing, international money transfer, and tracking software, mobile banking.
- Reg-tech – audit, risk, and regulatory compliance software.
- Personal finance – tools for managing bills, track personal and credit accounts.
- Insurance – companies are selling insurance digitally, and providing data analytics for reinsurance.
- Capital markets – buying and selling, trading analysis, and infrastructure tools for financial institutions.
- Biometrics – automatic identification of persons with the help of physiological and behavioral characteristics.

Challenges of Fin-Tech Technology

Fintech, in various industries, mainly banking and finance, principally faces three major challenges that must be tackled at the earliest.

- Security threat is one of the foremost challenges of the fin-tech industry: - The digitization of the banking and finance sector makes way for cyber attacks. Hence, the government and business firms must collaborate to make their systems secure enough to any kind of exposure of sensitive data.
- Knowledge and trust: - Customers must be able to accept and trust the changing systems. Fintech services have overcome the traditional way of banking and financial services, which is a major challenge for consumers with conservative mindsets.
- Lack of human touch: - Chat bots and AI are estimated to restore human contact. This could prove to be a main obstruction to the growth of various sectors, applying fin-tech technology to serve their customers. Thus, the companies must work to keep human touch as they strive to meet customer wants and satisfaction.
- Training to staff: - lack of training for staff for adaptation of new technology. Hence the business must focus on providing skill development and training to its employees.

Future of Fin-Tech in India

In a very short time the financial technology is reforming the lives of Indian citizens and is a step forward to the creation of the digital economy. In the era of “leadership”, the Fintech companies are bound to find several opportunities to capitalize and help in the economic growth of the country. The initiative taken by government of India has created a way for digital world. In addition to that, in an attempt to popularize cashless transactions, the government has offered tax rebates to traders that accept more than 50% of payment in through electronic payment system. The digitization of banks will make fin-tech technology the future of banking and financial sectors of India.

References/Bibliography

1. <http://www.academia.edu/Documents/in/Fintech>
2. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Financial_technology
3. <https://www.fintechweekly.com/fintech-definition>
4. <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/030315/what-financial-services-sector.asp>
5. <https://financialservices.gov.in/>
6. <https://www.siliconindia.com/news/general/Impact-of-fintech-in-India-nid-204284-cid-1.htm>